

Addressing Challenges in Textual Geolocation: Insights from Hebrew Place Descriptions

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Abstract. This work-in-progress explores the challenges of textual geolocation in Hebrew, a morphologically rich language with limited computational resources. Using a novel crowdsourced dataset, HeGeL (Hebrew GeoLocation), we analyze 5,695 place descriptions contributed by 1,554 participants, each relying on memory-based spatial cognition. The research reveals significant challenges in geolocating Hebrew textual descriptions due to linguistic ambiguities, such as vague spatial references, cardinal direction use, and limited gazetteer matches. This study proposes advancements for Hebrew and similar low-resource languages, providing pathways to improve spatial reasoning in Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks, emphasizing multilingual applicability and interdisciplinary collaboration.

Keywords. Textual geolocation, Hebrew, spatial cognition, natural language processing, geographic information retrieval.

1. Introduction

Textual geolocation, the process of deriving geographic coordinates from linguistic descriptions, is pivotal for applications in navigation, urban planning, and disaster management. Existing models rely heavily on named entity recognition (NER) and gazetteer matching, which falter in the absence of explicit place names or structured geographic cues (Mitkov, 2020). Hebrew, as a Semitic morphologically rich language (MRL), presents unique challenges for textual geolocation due to its complex syntax and reliance on spatial memory (Hayward & Tarr, 1995). This study focuses on analyzing natural place descriptions in

LBS 2025
19th Conference on Location Based Services
May 7-9, Otaniemi, Espoo, Finland

Published in "Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Location Based Services (LBS 2025)", edited by Juha Oksanen, Henrikki Tenkanen, Pyry Kettunen and Ville Mäkinen, LBS 2025 7-9 May 2025 Otaniemi, Espoo, Finland.

This contribution underwent double-blind peer review based on the paper.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15351059>
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Hebrew to bridge gaps in NLP models and improve Geographic Information Retrieval (GIR) applications.

2. Methodology

The HeGeL dataset was developed through a structured crowdsourcing approach, comprising:

- **Task 1:** Participants described familiar places from memory without explicit place names. Places were chosen based on their type, location in the city, distinct geometry, size (area), and context. All places serve as urban objects with different functions and experiences, such that they should produce different cognitive representations and hence different place descriptions related to scales, referencing frames and levels of spatial knowledge (Figure 1).
- **Task 2:** Other participants validated these descriptions by marking locations on a map (OpenStreetMap). Each place description was validated by at least two participants.

The dataset spans Israel’s three largest cities—Tel Aviv, Haifa, and Jerusalem—to capture diverse linguistic and spatial characteristics. Each city’s unique cultural and topographical features were reflected in the descriptions, offering a robust sample for geospatial analysis.

Figure 1. Place type percentage per city: Tel Aviv, Haifa, and Jerusalem.

2.1 Dataset details

- **Participant demographics:** The contributors included diverse age groups and linguistic backgrounds to ensure representation of varied spatial cognition and language use.

- **Data attributes:** The dataset includes textual descriptions, mapped locations, and associated metadata such as time of description and validation rates.
- **Validation process:** Descriptions were evaluated based on spatial accuracy, linguistic coherence, and participant agreement, ensuring high-quality data for analysis.

2.2 Challenges encountered

Creating the dataset required overcoming linguistic ambiguity and user bias. Some participants provided overly general descriptions, such as "near the city center," requiring additional validation rounds. Furthermore, the lack of established gazetteer entries for colloquial place names often led to discrepancies between participant interpretations and geospatial accuracy.

2.3 Data analysis

Quantitative methods, including error distance calculations, and qualitative techniques, such as linguistic pattern analysis, were employed. Key linguistic elements like prepositions, cardinal directions, and landmark mentions were categorized and analyzed. Preliminary results also indicated correlations between demographic factors and descriptive precision, highlighting the influence of language fluency, gender, and familiarity with urban environments.

3. Key Findings

- **Spatial vagueness:** Descriptions frequently relied on cardinal directions (e.g., "east of") and landmarks, increasing ambiguity in geolocating places. For instance, the phrase "near the old synagogue" often lacked specific positional data, creating challenges in precise mapping.
- **City-specific linguistics:** Vocabulary varied across cities due to morphological and topographical differences (Figure 2). Tel Aviv descriptions frequently included modern landmarks, such as skyscrapers, while Jerusalem descriptions relied on historical references, often tied to religious or cultural heritage. Moreover, Tel-Aviv and Haifa, which are located near the seashore, included usage of reference to water elements ("sea", "beach", "port"), while Haifa and Jerusalem, which are situated on a mountain, included usage of topographic and height-related elements ("ridge", "cable car", "overlook", "wadi").

Figure 2. Venn diagram of the top 10 used words.

- Geolocation accuracy:** Retrieval error analysis revealed challenges in map-matching Hebrew textual descriptions, with a median error of 314 meters. Notably, areas with dense, overlapping landmarks posed greater difficulties. Moreover, there was a clear correlation between the retrieval error and the clarity of description, as perceived by the participant locating the place on the map (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Place Boxplot representation of retrieval error by region. x-axis depicts the description clarity as chosen by mapper.

- Baseline models analysis:** We tested HeGel with a NER approach - could recognizing entities in a text and retrieving their corresponding coordinates be sufficient to solve textual geolocation tasks? To this end, we used Google Maps API¹ to produce two baseline models: Google Maps API Query with the full raw text descriptions, and Google Maps API Query with Oracle NER using 1-5 grams. Table 1 depicts the results, showing that the task is not solvable even with adequate resolution of the Google Maps API, where human performance provides the upper bound performance.

Model	Mean Distance [m]	Median Distance [m]
Google Maps API Query	2,804	850
Oracle NER	2,366	497
HUMAN	579	314

Table 1. Baselines for the textual geolocation task with the HeGeL corpus.

4. Discussion

This research underscores the critical need to develop NLP tools capable of handling spatially ambiguous languages like Hebrew. Incorporating spatial reasoning into NLP models can bridge existing gaps, particularly in low-resource languages (Tsarfaty et al., 2020). Additionally, the findings demonstrate the potential of crowdsourced geospatial data in revealing socio-linguistic patterns. Expanding these approaches to other MRLs, such as Arabic or Amharic, could further enhance multilingual geospatial applications.

One notable observation is the correlation between cultural familiarity and descriptive precision. Participants from Jerusalem, for instance, frequently referred to landmarks that were historically or religiously significant, whereas Tel Aviv participants tended to focus on modern urban features. This cultural variability highlights the importance of context-aware models in textual geolocation tasks. Moreover, this study opens avenues for interdisciplinary

¹ <http://code.google.com/apis/maps/>

collaboration between linguistics, computer science, and urban planning to create culturally adaptive geospatial solutions. Expanding the HeGeL dataset to include rural areas or less urbanized regions could provide additional insights into spatial cognition and geolocation patterns.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the complexities of Hebrew textual geolocation and underscores the need for advanced NLP models that integrate spatial reasoning. The HeGeL dataset serves as a benchmark for addressing these challenges and developing multilingual, culturally adaptive GIR solutions. Future work includes extending the dataset to other languages and refining NLP models for higher spatial resolution and reasoning capabilities. By enhancing our understanding of spatial language, this research contributes to the broader goal of making geospatial technologies more inclusive and effective.

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